

Table 1. Varietal reaction to leafhoppers and planthoppers, Varanasi, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a to			
	<i>N. lugens</i>	<i>S. furcifera</i>	<i>N. virescens</i>	<i>N. nigropictus</i>
OR34-16	S	MR	MR	MR
Jaya	MR	S	MR	S
CR202-2	S	MR	MR	MR
Culture 1	MR	MR	S	S
CR132-168-73	S	MR	S	MR
IR8	MR	S	MR	S
Saket 4	S	MR	MR	S
DR92	S	S	MR	S
RP79-24	S	S	MR	MR
Mtu 17	S	S	S	S
Nagina 22	S	S	MR	MR
RP79-27	S	S	S	S
CR142-2-10	S	S	S	S
RP79-5	S	S	S	S
Cauveri	S	MR	S	S
IR28	S	MR	S	MR
Pusa33	S	S	S	S
Jelhore	S	MR	S	MR
C7306	S	MR	S	S
FH109	S	S	S	S
IET5725	MR	MR	S	S
CR115-107	MR	S	S	S
TN1	S	S	S	S
Ptb 33	R	MR	MR	MR

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, and S = susceptible.

Table 2. Nymphal survival of rice leafhoppers and planthoppers on moderately resistant varieties at Varanasi, India.

Variety	Survival (%) of insect species ^a		
	<i>N. lugens</i>	<i>S. furcifera</i>	<i>Nephotettix</i> spp.
Jaya	63	—	73
IR28	—	67	87
RP79-24	—	—	70
Jelhore	83	77	73
IR8	70	—	77
OR34-16	—	67	73
CR202-2	—	80	73
Nagina 22	—	—	87
Saket 4	—	80	80
DR92	—	—	83
CR132-168-73	—	87	80
CR115-107	70	—	—
Culture	160	70	—
IET5725	67	77	—
Cauveri	—	57	—
C7306	—	73	—
TN1	97	100	100
Ptb33	43	47	53

^a— = not studied; a mixed population of *N. virescens* and *N. nigropictus* was used.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Performance of IR64 at Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TNRRI)

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IR64 (IR18348-36-3-3) was evaluated at TNRRI in the 1983 International Rice Yield Nursery-Early trial and in 1984 yield trials. IR64 matured in 110-115 d

Performance of IR64 at TNRRI, Aduthurai, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			Flowering duration (d)
	1983 kuruvai	1984 kuruvai		
		Trial 1	Trial 2	
IR64	3.4	5.6	5.3	65-70
TKM9	4.9	5.0	4.8	75-80
IR50	2.4	—	4.6	70-75
ADT36	—	—	4.7	80-85

and yielded 0.5 t/ha more than TKM9, IR50, and ADT36 (see table). It has short stature and long, slender grains, and is resistant to brown planthopper, gall midge, and yellowing syndrome, a serious disease in Tamil Nadu. ☞

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DEEP WATER

Elongation ability of deep water rice at two nitrogen levels

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Deep water Habiganj Aman II seeds

were sown in earthen pots with 8 kg soil and 0 or 8 g urea fertilizer per pot. The 5 replications had a pot each with 10 plants. Triple superphosphate and muriate of potash were applied at 5 g/pot. Five weeks after sowing, the pots were placed in concrete tanks,

flooded, and water was raised 10 cm/d for 9 d. A single seedling was taken from each pot every 2 d to record chlorophyll content and internode elongation.

Elongation rate of all plants increased for 4 d after flooding and then gradually

1. Plant height and internode elongation ability of Habiganj Aman II.

2. Change of total chlorophyll content of leaves of Habiganj Aman II during flooding.

decreased (Fig. 1). No-N plants were shorter than plants with N before flooding, but elongated more rapidly, indicating that ability of internodes to elongate is influenced more by

submergence depth rather than by N content. The no-N plants had lower final plant height.

Chlorophyll content of the three upper leaves of the no-N plants gradually increased during flooding

(Fig. 2). With added N, chlorophyll content decreased and then increased to slightly more than the initial content. Chlorophyll increased more rapidly in no-N plants than in those with added N. *S*

Pest Control and Management INSECTS

Whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) outbreak in Haryana, India

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WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* Horváth has attacked rice in Haryana since the early 1970s, and severe outbreaks occurred in 1984-85. We surveyed field

populations of WBPH in villages in Karnal, Kurukshetra, Ambala, Jind, Hisar, and Sirsa Districts in mid-Sep, when pest incidence was high and rice was at panicle emergence stage. Sixty of the 85 villages surveyed had more than 70% infestation and 15 villages had 18% infestation (see table). WBPH population was 100-2,000/hill. PR106 was the most affected variety. Weather was generally warm and humid. *S*

WBPH population intensity in Haryana, India, 1984-85.

District	Block	Villages surveyed (no.)	Villages (no.) with indicated intensity ^a		
			Severe	Moderate	Light
Karnal	Nilokheri	4	4	0	0
	Indri	6	6	0	0
	Karnal	3	2	1	0
	Jundla	5	5	0	0
	Assandh	6	4	1	1
Kurukshetra	Pundri	15	13	1	1
	Kaithal	7	7	0	0
	Sewan	4	4	0	0
	Cheeka	3	1	1	1
	Pehowa	2	1	1	0
Ambala	Ambala	2	1	1	0
	Naraingarh	2	0	1	1
	Bilashpur	1	0	1	0
	Jagadhari	2	0	2	0
Sirsa	Rania	12	5	4	3
	Kalait	4	—	1	3
Hisar	Tohana	4	4	0	0
	Ratia	3	3	0	0
Total		85	60	15	10

^aSevere = fields with one or more hopperburned patches; moderate = fields with yellowing; light no visible symptoms.

Need-based control of yellow stem borer (YSB)

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YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* Wlk. damages rice from tillering to maturity. We compared need-based control of YSB using egg masses as threshold criteria with scheduled control in 1983 and 1984 rainy seasons at NARP farm.